

A Study of Relationship between Burnout and Organizational Commitment among Secondary School Teachers of District Sonipat

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Abstract

The present study was conducted to explore the relationship between Burnout and Organizational Commitment among Secondary School Teachers of Sonipat District. This study was conducted on 200 teachers (100 males and 100 females). These teachers were selected randomly from Private and Govt. Secondary school of Sonipat District. A descriptive survey method was used to collect the data. In the present study, 'Teacher Burnout Scale' prepared by 'Dr. Madhu Gupta and Surekha Rani' and 'Organizational Commitment Questionnaire' prepared by 'Sh. Upinder Dhar, Sh. Prasant Mishra and D.K. Sirvastava' the standardized tools were used to collect the Data. For analyzing the Data descriptive statistical techniques namely mean, S.D., t-test and Co-efficient of Correlation were used. After analysis of the data it was found that there is a significant and negative relationship between Burnout and Organizational Commitment among Secondary School Teachers. The results reveals that the female teachers were more committed than male teachers. The results indicated that Govt. teachers were highly committed than the Private School teachers. The result indicated that Rural area School teachers were more committed than the Urban area school teachers.

Keywords Organizational Commitment, Burnout, Secondary School Teachers, Type of Institution, Geographical Location.

Introduction

According to ancient Indian beliefs, the position of a teacher is considered higher than God. Because it is the teacher who helps us to know the difference between right and wrong. A teacher is someone who helps others to learn, develop a skill or appreciate something. The progress and reputation of any school depends on the teachers of that school. The work of a teacher is considered very difficult and complex because teachers are responsible for shaping the future of children. It is also considered the responsibility of teachers to improve the behavior, habits and conduct of the students. Teachers are a positive force in society, who saves people from evil.

There is a close relationship between the development of education and the contribution of teachers to the progress of any nation. The contribution of teachers is more important in this because in the teaching process, both education and teachers are considered two sides of a coin. The success of any education system depends on the hard work of its teachers. Teachers are the soul of any school.

Burnout

The teaching process is considered incomplete without a teacher. To impart education effectively, the mind of the teacher should be stable and functioning smoothly. The teacher should be satisfied with his profession. The workload of a teacher should be reasonable and not excessively burdensome so that he can do his job effectively. The teaching process should run smoothly. If a teacher is not mentally healthy and strong, then his ability to work will also deteriorate and he will not be able to do his work honestly. Imposing excessive workload on teachers leads to problems like burnout.

When a person begins to experience negative thoughts and feels sluggish and tired, he or she is said to be suffering from burnout. The word "burnout" is an English term which means inactive, broken, lacking fuel, agitated or angry. Burnout is a state of mental and physical exhaustion due to excessive workload, which may arise due to a lack of interest in work. In case of burnout, there is unbearable physical pain and the person becomes angry. He or She experiences feelings of irritability and may become practically incontinent.

According to Herbert and Ford Berger (2012) :-

"Burnout is a state of physical, mental and emotional exhaustion resulting from chronic stress, which causes motivation or inspiration to disappear."

According to India Today Web Desk :-

"Burnout or chronic work-related stress can be difficult to identify because it slowly creeps up on you over a long period of time. This is why it is often challenging to seek help because it is difficult to recognize that you may be suffering from this acute symptom of chronic stress. Burnout depletes all coping resources and increases stress-related side effects such as psychosomatic illnesses, etc. It refers to chronic tiredness or fatigue, lack of energy."

In recent decades, mental health-related problems have emerged among teachers in many Educational Institutions. The problem of Burnout, which refers to a state of chronic stress that leads to a teacher's depletion of emotional energy and personal behavior. Chronic stress leads to burnout among teachers. Due to which sadness and negative emotions arise in them. These negative emotions in teachers arise due to the indifference of their students. They experience burnout syndrome due to chronic stress.

Teacher burnout affects his or her health in various ways, causing anxiety, irritability, fatigue, and emotional exhaustion. As a result, negative emotions like irritability, resentment and anger may develop in his behavior. Negativity prevails in the teacher's mind. The mind remains disturbed. All these things point towards emotional stress and poor health.

According to Ashtam (2001) "An estimated 50% of workers in India suffer from stress. Therefore, it is important to understand the stress of those who have made teaching their profession."

Organizational Commitment :-

Organizational commitment indicates the relationship or bond of an employee with his organization. It is based on organizational psychology and it describes the psychological attachment of a person to his organization. It can be defined as a member's psychological attitude of attachment to an organization in which a person works. Organizational commitment plays a vital role in determining that any employee will remain employed in that organization for a long time and will work with full devotion and dedication and fostering a sense of self-dedication to fulfill the goals set by that organization.

According to Wikipedia :-

"In Organizational behavior and industrial and Organizational Psychology, Organizational Commitment is an individual's psychological attachment to the Organization".

According to Oxford review Encyclopedia :-

"Organizational commitment is the individual's psychological attachment to an Organization. Usually Organizational Commitment and Job Satisfaction are closely correlated together with lower levels of intention to leave the Organization."

If organizational commitment of an employee is determined then it can be done on the basis of job satisfaction, employee's attachment towards the organization, sense of leadership, job performance, etc. The level of organizational commitment of any employee towards his work is very important to know or assess from the management point of view. So that a person can easily perform his assigned tasks on daily basis. **O'Reilly (1991)** said about organizational commitment that "Commitment as an individual's Psychological bond to the Organization including a sense of Job-involvement, loyalty and a belief in the values of the Organization." **Mariodos(2000)** "Commitment is a deep profound value of

emotional Intelligence. It means aligning with the goals of a group or organization and applying one self completely for a cause.”

When a teacher feels a strong sense of organizational commitment to his or her school or organization, the school also begins to view those teachers as a part of its organization professionally and personally and the organization trusts them to perform the tasks set by the school, which will assist the school in completing the goals on time. However, organizational commitment has been considered to have a positive relationship with job satisfaction. As soon as a person is satisfied with his work, his organizational commitment also increases day by day. As organizational commitment increases, the work efficiency of teachers also increases. Their attachment to the organization also grows. As this attachment increases, his morale also starts increasing. With all these factors increasing, the chances of the employee staying in that organization for a long time increase. The teacher does not repeatedly entertain the thought of leaving one school and going to another. Committed employees display more positive behavior, greater determination and motivation.

A committed teacher has high productivity. He displays a high level of productivity to accomplish the goals of the organization. A committed and motivated teacher will report far fewer absences than his/her peers. These teachers are always ready to help the organization in completing its projects. This emotional attachment of a teacher towards his school does not motivate him to go to any other school and he is forced to work in the same institution for a long time. Teachers are also like an asset for a school from which children get education and it is these teachers who provide their full co-operation in achieving the goals set by the school.

Ultimately, we can say that organizational commitment is the psychological attachment of any teacher towards his work place and the fulfill of the goals set by his school. They have a deep dedication towards his organization and prefer to remain a part of it for a long time. Sometimes, while fulfilling these goals, a teacher may be given a workload beyond their capacity which can lead to professional stress. Due to being under stress for a long time, the teacher sometimes does not even realize when this stress takes the severe form of burnout. Due to which his work gets affected. This has a direct impact on his working capacity and productivity. Due to which both the school and its students are equally affected. To prevent this organization should assign work to their teachers according to their capacity and qualifications. So that they can do their work smoothly on time and both the students and the school get benefits.

Objective of study

The present study was conducted to explore the relationship between Burnout and Organizational Commitment among Secondary School Teachers of Sonipat District.

1. To find out the relationship between Burnout and Organizational Commitment among Secondary School Teachers of Sonipat District.
2. To study the Organizational Commitment of Secondary School Teachers of Sonipat District on the basis of Gender.
3. To study the Organizational Commitment of Secondary School Teachers of Sonipat District on the basis of type of Institution.
4. To study the Organizational Commitment of Secondary school Teachers of Sonipat District on the basis of Geographical location.

Review of Literature

Bhardwaj (2014) conducted a study on the topic "Burnout among secondary school teachers and its impact on teacher effectiveness" on a sample of 160 teachers teaching in secondary schools of Solan district of Himachal Pradesh and concluded that burnout level of secondary teachers, teaching is much affected by experience and mode of appointment. There is no significant effect of burnout on teacher effectiveness.

Antonio and Others (2013) conducted a study titled "Occupational Stress and Professional Burnout in Elementary and Secondary School Teachers." As a sample, he selected 388 educators for this purpose. After analyzing the collected data, it was determined that primary teachers were more stressed than secondary teachers, while female teachers were more stressed than male teachers.

Srivastava (2013) investigated the relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment using 247 middle-level managers from the B.P.O., banking, and information technology sectors. For measuring organizational commitment, Mode, Steers, and Potter's (1979) and Paul E. Spector's (1985) work satisfaction survey was

utilized. The study discovered a correlation between middle-level manager’s job satisfaction and organizational commitment.

Methodology

Descriptive survey method has been used in the present research.

Sampling

In the present research work, teachers working in government and non-government secondary schools of Sonipat District selected by random method for the sample.

Tools Used

The researcher used two standardized instruments for this research work.

These standardized test will be used for collecting the Data :-

1. 'Organizational Commitment Questionnaire' prepared by (Sh. Upinder Dhar & Sh. Prasant Mishra and Sh. D.K. Sirvastava)
2. 'Teacher Burnout Scale' prepared by (Madhu Gupta and Surekha Rani)

Variables of the study :-

The two types of Variables were included in this research.

1. Independent Variable : Burnout
2. Dependent Variable : Organizational Commitment

Statistics Used in the Study

For fulfillment of the objectives of the study descriptive statistical techniques namely mean, S.D., t-test and Correlation were applied.

Result and Discussion

Objective 1:- To find out the relationship between Burnout and Organizational Commitment among Secondary school Teachers of Sonipat District.

Table 1.1

The relationship between Burnout and Organizational Commitment among Secondary school Teachers of Sonipat District.

Variable	No. of Teacher	R	β	Significant level	Result
Burnout V/s Organizational Commitment	200	.117	-.117	0.001	Significant (Rejected)

Interpretation :- It shows that there is a significant relationship between Burnout and Organizational Commitment of Secondary School Teachers where R value is .117 and β value is -.117 which means there is a negative relationship between Burnout and Organizational commitment i.e. β = - .117 that means Burnout leads to decline in Organizational Commitment by more than 11%. The significant value is less than 0.01 i.e. 0.001 which is significant and null hypothesis "There is no significant relationship between burnout and Organizational Commitment among Secondary School Teachers" was rejected.

Objective 2 :- To study the Organizational Commitment of Secondary school Teachers of Sonipat District on the basis of Gender.

Table : 1.2

Comparison of Organizational Commitment of Secondary School Teachers of Sonipaat District on the basis of Gender.

Gender	No. of Teacher	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	Significant Level	Remark
Female	100	35.21	4.411	198	2.890	0.05	Significant
Male	100	33.15	5.598				

Fig.1.2

Interpretation :- Table & fig. 1.2 indicates that the mean score of Organizational Commitment of female and male teachers of secondary school are 35.21 and 33.15 with standard deviation 4.411 and 5.598 respectively. The t-value come out from the above two groups is 2.890 and the critical value of 't' at the level of significance is 1.97. Hence the t-value is greater than the critical value. Hence it is significant. Therefore the null hypothesis "There is no significant difference between Organizational Commitment of Secondary school teachers of Sonipat District on the basis of Gender." was rejected at the significant level of 0.05.

Objective 3: To study the Organizational Commitment of Secondary School Teachers of Sonipat District on the basis of type of Institution.

Table 1.3

Comparison of Organizational Commitment of Secondary School Teachers of Sonipat District on the basis of type of Institution.

Institution	No. of Teacher	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	Significant Level	Remark
Govt.	100	36.52	3.218	198	5.535	0.05	Significant
Private	100	33.58	4.226				

Fig.1.3

Interpretation :- Table and fig.1.3 indicates that the mean score of Organizational Commitment of Govt. and Private Secondary School Teachers are 36.52 and 33.58 with standard deviation 3.218 and 4.226 respectively. The t-value come out from the above two groups is 5.535 and the critical value of 't' at the level of significance is 1.97. Hence the t-value is greater then the critical value. Hence it is significant. Therefore the null Hypothesis "There is no significant difference between Organizational Commitment of Secondary School Teachers of Sonipat District" was rejected at the significance level of 0.05.

Objective 4: To study the Organizational Commitment of Secondary School Teachers of Sonipat District on the basis of Geographical Location.

Table 1.4

Comparison of Organizational Commitment of Secondary School Teachers of Sonipat District on the basis of Geographical Location.

Area	No. of Teacher	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	Significant Level	Remark
Rural	100	36.52	3.218	198	4.319	0.05	Significant
Urban	100	34.20	4.302				

Fig.1.4

Interpretation:- Table & figure 1.4 reveals that the mean score of organizational commitment of Urban area and Rural area Secondary School Teachers are 36.52 and 34.20 with standard deviation 3.218 and 4.302 respectively. The t-value come out from the above two groups is 4.319 and critical value of 't' at the level of significance is 1.97. hence the t-value is greater than the critical value. Hence it is significant. Therefore the null Hypothesis "There is no significant difference between Organizational commitment of Secondary School Teachers of Sonipat district on the basis of Geographical location" was rejected at significant level of 0.05.

Findings

1. It was found that there is a significant relationship between burnout and organizational commitment of secondary school teachers of Sonipat District. The result shows that there is a negative relationship between Burnout and Organizational Commitment among secondary school teachers.
2. In regards to organizational commitment between female and male teachers of secondary school of Sonipat District. The present study indicates that there is a significant difference in Organizational Commitment among female and male teachers of secondary school. The mean value of female teachers is 35.21 which is more than the male teachers.
3. In regards to organizational commitment between Govt. and Private secondary school teachers of Sonipat District. The present study reveals that there is a significant difference in Organizational commitment among Govt. and Private secondary school teachers of Sonipat District. The mean value of Govt. school teachers is 36.52 which is more than the Private school teachers.
4. In regards to Organizational Commitment between Rural and Urban Area secondary school teachers of Sonipat District. The present study reveals that there is a significant difference in Organizational Commitment among Rural Area and Urban Area secondary school teachers. The mean value of Rural Area school teachers is 36.52 which is more than the Urban Area school teachers.

Conclusion

This study reveals the actual position of teachers in relation to Burnout and Organizational Commitment among secondary school teachers of Sonipat District. There is a Significant and negative relationship were found in between Burnout and Organizational Commitment of secondary school teachers. Burnout leads to decline in Organizational Commitment by more than 11%. The mean indicates that female teachers are more committed towards their work as compared to male teachers. In comparison of Govt. and Private school teachers the Govt. school teachers are more committed than the Private School Teachers. In comparison of Rural and Urban Area School Teachers the Rural Area school teachers are more committed than Urban Area school teachers.

The level of burnout has also been found to be higher among teachers who have higher organizational commitment than usual. Burnout, which is a negative factor, increases as it reduces organizational commitment. Teachers who have high levels of organizational commitment are dedicated towards their work and always have a feeling of attachment towards their institution. Therefore, schools or organizations should also pay more

attention to ensure that the organizational commitment of teachers remains the same. It is also the responsibility of the organization to provide an environment in which teachers can work independently as per the needs of their employees. Organizations should also take care that their employees do not suffer from negative emotions like burnout or occupational stress. Stress free teachers can do their work smoothly.

Suggestions for the future Study Few suggestions for further Research are :-

1. This study was conducted on a sample of 200 Secondary School Teachers. The study could be conducted on a larger sample.
2. The present study was carried out in only the Sonipat District of Haryana. It may be carried out in other states. It may be on two or more districts.
3. The present study was confined to only secondary school teachers. A similar study can be conducted on primary or secondary school teachers or college cadres.

Limitation of the Study

1. The present study was delimited to 200 teachers of Secondary school only.
2. The study was confined to Sonipat District only.

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